

ENERGY EFFICIENCY SCALE

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Annotation: The article under consideration analyzes the production process on the example of the "Korasuv cotton cleaning" enterprise

Key words: energy saving, energy efficiency improvement, Energy efficiency scale, a sophisticated approach

Description:

The transition of Uzbekistan to the standards of well-being of developed countries requires an increase in the efficiency of the use of all types of energy resources. One of the most important mechanisms for increasing the energy efficiency of the activities of a modern industrial enterprise is the energy service

From 2011, under the Ministry of Economy and Industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to emphasize the project "Improving the energy efficiency of industrial enterprises". they had the opportunity to significantly reduce their wealth.

Reducing production costs and increasing the competitiveness of manufactured products is one of the most urgent issues for enterprises. Today, 82 sub-projects on increasing the energy efficiency of industrial enterprises have been successfully implemented. Projects are being implemented in energy-related fields such as oil and gas, mining, chemistry, electricity, construction and processing. More than 500 million kilowatt-hours of electricity and 187 million cubic meters of natural gas were saved per year as a result of the implementation of projects by more than 30 large industrial

enterprises. In addition, the release of carbon dioxide (CO₂) into the atmosphere was reduced by 580,000 tons per year

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In our country, every producer has the opportunity to modernize production within the framework of the project "Improving the energy efficiency of industrial enterprises".

Taking care of the enterprise starts with solving the issue of energy efficiency!

The energy efficiency of enterprises, organizations, energy facilities, and industrial sectors showed wide diversity and great differences in the actual state of affairs. Some enterprises use the obtained energy resources very efficiently, others show a very low indicator. Some enterprises have complete graphs of energy saving, action plans are being implemented, and individual workers are encouraged to use energy resources efficiently. Other companies are doing almost nothing in this direction. The results of the energy audit, of course, provide an objective assessment of the state of the work and the work being carried out. Under such conditions, a basic classification of energy saving objects seems necessary. It can be built on the basis of an objective measure that allows one or another state of the enterprise to be included in a certain group, category of efficiency. The introduction of such a scale gives a classification rule.

The main principles of the construction of the scale can be formulated as follows:

- classification of objects is carried out according to a single rule for everyone;
- high energy efficiency gives a high rating, low efficiency - a low rating;
- all used energy sources are evaluated;

assessment does not depend on the volume of used energy sources;

- the assessment is equally affected by the state of the energy-consuming object and the level of ensuring efficient use of energy resources;

It is not desirable to establish reference, reference marks for the application of measurement in all cases, for which certain numerical values can be uniquely adjusted. Such points can be zero scale and maximum scale.

The high, maximum, point should probably correspond to the beneficial use of all the energy expended. An example of this is the "engine". Another, lower reference point can serve as an object, where energy is wasted, wasted. According to the accepted classification, the scale in question belongs to the class of absolute scale. can be because it has absolute zero and absolute unity. This feature allows you to perform any algebraic and logical operations on absolute metrics, including you can use these metrics as exponents and arguments of logarithms. It is difficult to say today whether there is a need for such use of energy efficiency scale indicators.

Thus, the entire scale is located between the values of 0 - 100, and its intermediate values are formed according to the following priorities:

Objects, organizations, systems, technologies, devices are highly valued if they are characterized by:

- 1) high level of power plant efficiency;
- 2) low loss of energy and energy resources;
- 3) existence of an effective management system of measurement, control, accounting and regulation of energy sources;
- 4) low level of energy intensity of products, low level of specific costs of energy resources;
- 5) availability and effective implementation of the energy transfer program, plans of organizational and technical activities are managed by energy saving, energy and fuel balance;
- 6) availability of the energy passport of the energy industry and regularly conducted energy surveys;
- 7) availability of energy saving promotion system;
- 10) standardization in the field of energy saving and use of energy resources.

The methodology for evaluating the efficiency of the use of energy resources of an enterprise or organization is to allocate an integrated efficiency indicator (IPE):

$$IPE = \sum K_i S_j, (3)$$

where IPE is an integral indicator of efficiency; C_j is the value of one of the above efficiency criteria; K_i - i is the weighting factor of the efficiency criterion

Development of energy saving recommendations

Energy-saving recommendations are developed by applying the usual energy-saving methods to objects identified in the analysis phase with inefficient use of energy resources.

When developing recommendations, the following is necessary:

- Determining the technical nature of the proposed improvement and the principle of obtaining savings;

- calculate the potential annual savings, both physical and monetary

Determine the composition of the equipment necessary to implement the recommendations, its estimated cost, delivery, installation and commissioning costs;

- consider all possibilities of cost reduction, for example, production and installation of equipment by the enterprise, organization, institution itself;

- Determination of possible side effects from the implementation of recommendations affecting real economic efficiency;

- assessment of the overall economic effect of the proposed recommendation, taking into account all of the above

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